

JBIMA Editorial

Prof Sharif Kaf Al-Ghazal, Editor in Chief

Assalamo Alaikom

I thought I'd use this JBIMA editorial to reflect on the journey we have all been on as BIMA marks its 10-year anniversary this summer. Subhana Allah; What a 10 years it's been!

So many have dedicated countless hours in the service of BIMA, and ultimately, in the service of Allah, working only with the best of intentions. When I reflect and think of how far we've come, and the initial efforts of Dr Hammad Lodhi a decade ago, I'm exceptionally proud. What we have achieved together and the impact we've had on the Muslim and non-Muslim community alike has been astounding. From the lifesaver workshops we ran in mosques, to the work we did on organ donation and end of life care, we have so much to be proud about.

I must point out that if it weren't for the presence of BIMA - and for the work you all did as committed volunteers - I dread to think how much worse the covid pandemic would have been for the Muslim community. The guidance we offered mosques was crucial and our efforts in encouraging vaccine uptake were critical. This was a phenomenal achievement. The work that BIMA did during the pandemic was highlighted positively in the media and our collaborations with the MCB and other organisations was a great success.

As a former president I feel privileged to have been tasked with leading BIMA, developing it, and safeguarding the organisation for my successor, Dr Salman Waqar. You all taught me how to be an effective leader, and you offered your support when I needed it. This will never be forgotten.

Our mission, our vision and our unity has kept us strong. As Allah swt says in the Quran "And hold firmly to the rope of Allah all together and do not become divided".

We have held together; we have progressed and moved forwards because of the work you have all put in and the dedication you have demonstrated, and ultimately, because Allah willed it to be. There is no reason why the next decade can't be even better; we've laid our foundations and now we need to continue developing and facing the challenges the next few years will bring.

May Allah always keep us on the right path. May he always bless us and grant us success, and May he accept all that we do in his service.

Very best wishes,

Wassalam.

Prof. Sharif Kaf Al-Ghazal
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